

Synthesis, magnetic and spectral properties of binuclear imidazolate bridged copper(II)-copper(II) and copper(II)-zinc(II) complexes

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Two new binuclear imidazolate bridged complexes, [(PAN)Cu(im)Cu(PAN)](ClO₄)₂ and [(PAN)Cu(im)Zn(PAN)](ClO₄)₂ (PAN = 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol, im = imidazolate) have been prepared. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility of [(PAN)Cu(im)Cu(PAN)](ClO₄)₂ reveals the presence of intramolecular antiferromagnetic interactions through the imidazolate bridge. X-Band EPR spectra of some Cu^{II} mononuclear and Cu-Zn binuclear complexes have been reported. In solution (100%, DMSO, LNT), the imidazolate bridge of the complex [(PAN)Cu(im)Zn(PAN)]²⁺ breaks on zinc side. The formation of mononuclear and binuclear complexes has been confirmed by spectrometry.

1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN), a tridentate ligand containing an azo group, a heterocyclic nitrogen atom and a hydroxy group *ortho* to the azo group, is known to form the 1 : 1 copper-PAN complex¹ having composition [Cu(PAN)H₂O]ClO₄. Shibata² reported that when complexation occurs between copper(II) and PAN, two five-membered chelate rings are formed. Imidazole is a ligand of biological importance involved in active sites of metalloenzymes as a part of histidine moiety³. Imidazolate, the deprotonated form of imidazole, is involved in active site of bovine erythrocyte superoxide dismutase⁴. To explore the properties of imidazolate-bridged binuclear complexes, model complexes of the pairs copper-copper⁵, copper-cobalt⁶ and copper-zinc⁷ have been synthesized.

This paper describes the preparation, magnetic and spectral properties of some mononuclear copper(II) and homo/heterobinuclear complexes with 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol and imidazole.

Results and Discussion

All the solid complexes (Table 1) are air-stable at room temperature. The complexes are insoluble in most of the organic solvents except partially in DMF and DMSO, hence their molar conductance could not be measured. The elemental analysis data reveal a stoichiometry of 1 : 1 (M : L₁) for mononuclear and 2 : 2 : 1 (M : L₁ : L₂) for binuclear complexes.

Magnetic properties :

The room temperature magnetic susceptibility was measured. The two parent mononuclear complexes show normal magnetic moments (~1.7 B.M.) corresponding to one unpaired spin in copper(II). For homobinuclear com-

plex, antiferromagnetic exchange interaction is present as indicated by the effective magnetic moment (1.41 B.M.). The magnetic moment for heterobinuclear complex (1.80 B.M.) is in agreement with a one-spin system ($S = 1/2$).

EPR spectra :

Systems involving interaction between unpaired spins of two copper(II) centres (each $S = 1/2$), give rise to singlet ($S = 0$) and triplet ($S = 1$) states. The spin Hamiltonian for the triplet state interacting with a magnetic field H is given by

$$H = g\beta HS + Ds_z^2 + E(S_x^2 - S_y^2) - (2/3)D$$

where, D and E are zero field splitting parameters. Such a system should exhibit six EPR transitions at the magnetic fields defined below⁸.

$$H_{x1}^2 = (g_e/g_x)^2 [(H_0 - D' + E')(H_0 + 2E')]$$

$$H_{y1}^2 = (g_e/g_y)^2 [(H_0 - D' - E')(H_0 - 2E')]$$

$$H_{z1}^2 = (g_e/g_z)^2 [(H_0 - D')^2 - (E')^2]$$

$$H_{x2}^2 = (g_e/g_x)^2 [(H_0 - D' - E')(H_0 - 2E')]$$

$$H_{y2}^2 = (g_e/g_y)^2 [(H_0 + D' + E')(H_0 + 2E')]$$

$$H_{z2}^2 = (g_e/g_z)^2 [(H_0 + D')^2 - (E')^2]$$

where, $H_0 = hv/g_e$, $D' = D/g_e\beta$, $E' = E/g_e$ and H_{x1} and H_{x2} are for example the $\Delta M = \pm 1$ resonance field, when the magnetic field is along the x -direction; g_e is the free electron g -value. In addition, a signal corresponding to $\Delta M = \pm 2$ transition should also be observed when $D < hv$. Observed EPR transitions for various complexes and their assignments are given in Table 1.

[Cu(PAN)H₂O]ClO₄ : This complex shows similar EPR spectra (polycrystalline) at room temperature as well as at

liquid nitrogen temperature. There is no apparent difference in either the spectral features or the spectral parameters at two temperatures. At both temperatures complex gives broad signal in the low field region, indicating spin-exchange interactions between the copper ions⁹ and therefore, hyperfine splitting is lost. From these spectra two transitions, viz. H_1 and H_2 were observed and the corresponding g -value evaluated. Obtained resonance fields and EPR parameters are given in Table 1.

Table 1. EPR resonance fields (G) and EPR parameters of complexes*

Compd	Temp.	H_{TCNE}	H_1	H_2	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}
[Cu(PAN)H ₂ O]ClO ₄	RT	3390	3120	3345	2.176	2.029
	LNT	3225	2960	3190	2.182	2.024
[Cu(PAN)imH]ClO ₄	RT	3395	3160	3335	2.151	2.038
	LNT	3230	3010	3170	2.149	2.049
[(PAN)Cu(im)-Cu(PAN)](ClO ₄) ₂	RT		(III resolved)			
	LNT	3240	2880	3150	2.253	2.060
			(H_{\parallel})	(H_{\perp})	(g_{\parallel})	(g_{\perp})
[(PAN)Cu(im)-Zn(PAN)](ClO ₄) ₂	RT	3390	3280(H_{iso})		2.069(g_{iso})	
	LNT	3245	3140(H_{iso})		2.069(g_{iso})	

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and metal analyses.

[Cu(PAN)imH]ClO₄ : This complex shows the similar EPR features (polycrystalline) and parameters to that of [Cu(PAN)H₂O]ClO₄. The EPR parameters are presented in Table 1. The EPR spectrum of this complex was also recorded in frozen solution (in DMSO) at liquid nitrogen temperature. The solution EPR parameters and bonding coefficients were evaluated (Table 2). The value of g is less than 2.3, thereby indicating the covalent nature of the complex. Also the value of out-of-plane σ -bonding (α^2) is 0.70. This value of α^2 indicates for covalent nature¹⁰ of the complex. Other bonding parameters also indicate its covalent nature.

[(PAN)Cu(im)Cu(PAN)](ClO₄)₂ : The X-band EPR spectra (polycrystalline) of this compound provide additional convincing support for the presence of a weak exchange interaction. At room temperature the complex gives a broad signal in the low field side, thereby indicating spin-exchange interactions between two copper ions¹⁰. Due to spin-exchange interactions the hyperfine splitting is lost. On cooling to liquid nitrogen temperature, the spectrum (solution) shows four lines with two g -values (Table 2), which is attributed to a predominantly $d_{x^2-y^2} - d_{z^2}$ ground state with tetragonal distortion around the copper(II) ion. This is further confirmed by $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ value¹¹ (159 cm⁻¹) which falls in the range for tetragonal distorted complexes (150–250 cm⁻¹).

[(PAN)Cu(im)Zn(PAN)](ClO₄)₂ : At room temperature as well as at liquid nitrogen temperature the spectra are nearly isotropic ($g_{iso} = 2.069$, Table 2). On cooling to liquid nitrogen temperature, no structural change was observed. No $\Delta M_S = \pm 2$ signal was detected at 'half field', thereby indicating the absence of Cu-im-Cu impurity⁵.

In solution (100% DMSO, LNT) EPR spectrum was recorded. The values of solution parameters evaluated are given in Table 2. It may be noted that the frozen solution of [(PAN)Cu(im)Zn(PAN)]²⁺ exhibits an EPR spectrum nearly similar to that of the frozen solution of [Cu(PAN)imH]ClO₄. In solution, therefore, the imidazolate bridge appears to break on the zinc(II) side⁷ (eq. 1),

The value of g_{\parallel} comes out to be 2.234, which is less than 2.3, hence, the nature of complex is covalent. The value of out-of-plane σ -bonding (α^2) is found to be 0.71, thereby, again indicating the covalent behaviour¹⁰ of the complex. Similar behaviour may also be extracted on the basis of other bonding parameters (Table 2).

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra (nujol) of the complexes were also recorded. The λ_{max} value (13700 cm⁻¹) of [Cu(PAN)imH]ClO₄ is greater than that (13640 cm⁻¹) of [Cu(PAN)H₂O]ClO₄ as expected from ligand field consideration. With imidazole as the fourth ligand, the whole electronic spectrum shifted towards higher energy. In case of dinuclear complexes, there are two λ_{max} value for each. The λ_{max} values which falls in the range 12500–12700 cm⁻¹ are ascribable to $d-d$ transition. The other λ_{max} values lie in the 25000–27000 cm⁻¹ region, which is possibly due to the M-im-M bonding¹².

Experimental

1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (Riedel), imidazole (s.d. Fine-chem), copper perchlorate hexahydrate (Aldrich) and nickel perchlorate hexahydrate (Aldrich) were used as supplied. Other chemicals used were of reagent grade.

[Cu(PAN)H₂O]ClO₄ : In ethanol-water mixture (1 : 1), the solutions of Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (740 mg, 2 mmol; 50 ml) and PAN (498 mg, 2 mmol; 50 ml) were mixed and stirred for 0.5 h and the contents left overnight. The resulting dark red coloured complex of [Cu(PAN)H₂O]ClO₄ was washed

Table 2. EPR parameters and bonding coefficient of some Cu^{II} complexes

Complex	$H_{TCNE}(G)$	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	$A_{\parallel}(G)$	α^2	α'^2	β^2	δ^2	a	b
[Cu(PAN)imH]ClO ₄	3220	2.227	2.047	160	0.70	0.39	0.76	0.65	1.85	0.36
[(PAN)Cu(im)Zn(PAN)](ClO ₄) ₂	3235	2.234	2.053	160	0.71	0.38	0.82	0.76	2.07	0.45

with ether and dried in calcium chloride desiccator at room temperature (yield 70%), m.p. 215°.

[Cu(PAN)imH]ClO₄ : In ethanol-water mixture (1 : 1), the solutions of Cu(ClO₄)₂.6H₂O (740 mg, 2 mmol; 50 ml), PAN (498 mg, 2 mmol; 50 ml) and imH (136 mg, 2 mmol; 50 ml) were mixed and stirred well for 0.5 h and the contents left overnight. The resulting red coloured complex of [Cu(PAN)imH]ClO₄ was washed with ether and dried in calcium chloride desiccator at room temperature (yield 65%), m.p. 210°.

[(PAN)Cu(im)Zn(PAN)](ClO₄)₂ : In ethanol-water mixture (1 : 1), the solutions of Cu(ClO₄)₂.6H₂O (740 mg, 2 mmol; 50 ml), PAN (498 mg, 2 mmol; 50 ml) and imH (136 mg, 2 mmol; 50 ml) were mixed and stirred (Set-A). Similarly, in ethanol-water mixture (1 : 1), the solutions of Zn(ClO₄)₂.6H₂O (744 mg, 2 mmol; 50 ml) and PAN (498 mg, 2 mmol; 50 ml) were mixed and stirred (Set-B). Contents of Set-A and Set-B were then mixed and stirred. pH of the solution was raised to 12.0 by adding 1M NaOH solution and the contents were left overnight. The resulting light red coloured complex of [(PAN)Cu(im)Zn(PAN)](ClO₄)₂ was washed with ether and dried in calcium chloride desiccator at room temperature (yield 65%), m.p. 220°.

The complex [(PAN)Cu(im)Cu(PAN)](ClO₄)₂ was prepared by similar method, m.p. 205°.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy Balance using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as calibrating agent ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units). EPR spectra were recorded with a Varian E-line Century series spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band with 100 kHz modulation. TCNE ($g = 2.00277$) was used as field marker. The frozen samples were placed in a Varian liquid nitrogen Dewar flask for measurement at 77 K. The g_{\parallel} and A_{\parallel} values were measured according to the standard procedure¹³. EPR spectra of frozen samples did not exhibit well-resolved g . The g values at the maximum absorption (g_m), which is close to g_{\perp} ¹⁴, were measured instead. Bonding parameters were evaluated by using Kivelson and Neiman method¹⁵. Electronic spectra were recorded with a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer using matched 1 cm path length quartz cells.

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